

Khmelnik S.I.ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1493-6630>

Solving Maxwell's Equations for AC Wire

Annotation

It is indicated that an electromagnetic wave propagates in an AC wire. The well-known solution of Maxwell's equations in the form of a wave equation is not acceptable, if only because in such a solution the law of conservation of energy is fulfilled only on average.

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1. Introduction

At present, the applicability of Maxwell's equations to all phenomena of electrodynamics and electrical devices without exception is indisputable. However, it is not always possible to describe these phenomena and devices in the form of a solution to the complete system of Maxwell's equations, and not a certain subset of this system. The same applies to the AC wire. Below, an electromagnetic wave in an alternating current wire is described as a solution to the full system of Maxwell's equations. It is important to note that the well-known solution of Maxwell's equations in the form of a wave equation is not acceptable, if only because in such a solution the energy conservation law is fulfilled only on average.

Maxwell's equations for vacuum cannot be used directly for AC wire, since the wire has conduction currents and dielectric constant. In the case under consideration, Maxwell's equations have the form:

$$\operatorname{rot}(E) + \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\operatorname{rot}(H) - I = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\operatorname{div}(E) = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\operatorname{div}(H) = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$\operatorname{div}(I) = 0, \quad (5)$$

where E is electric intensity, H is magnetic intensity, I is conduction currents, μ - absolute magnetic permeability.

2. Solving Maxwell's Equations

In the system of cylindrical coordinates, these equations have the form:

$$\frac{E_r}{r} + \frac{\partial E_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial E_\phi}{\partial \phi} + \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \phi} - \frac{\partial E_\phi}{\partial z} = \frac{\mu\omega}{c} \frac{dH_r}{dt}, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_r}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial r} = \frac{\mu\omega}{c} \frac{dH_\phi}{dt}, \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{E_\phi}{r} + \frac{\partial E_\phi}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial E_r}{\partial \phi} = \frac{\mu\omega}{c} \frac{dH_z}{dt}, \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{H_r}{r} + \frac{\partial H_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial H_\phi}{\partial \phi} + \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \phi} - \frac{\partial H_\phi}{\partial z} = I_r, \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_r}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial r} = I_\phi, \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{H_\phi}{r} + \frac{\partial H_\phi}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial H_r}{\partial \phi} = I_z, \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{I_r}{r} + \frac{\partial I_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial I_\phi}{\partial \phi} + \frac{\partial I_z}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (9)$$

We will search for unknown functions in the following form:

$$H_r = h_r(r) \text{co}, \quad (10)$$

$$H_\phi = h_\phi(r) \text{si}, \quad (11)$$

$$H_z = h_z(r) \text{si}, \quad (12)$$

$$E_r = e_r(r) \text{si}, \quad (13)$$

$$E_\phi = e_\phi(r) \text{co}, \quad (14)$$

$$E_z = e_z(r) \text{co}, \quad (15)$$

$$I_r = i_r(r) \text{sic}, \quad (16)$$

$$I_\phi = i_\phi(r) \text{coc}, \quad (17)$$

$$I_z = i_z(r) \text{sic}, \quad (18)$$

where

$$\text{co} = \cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z) \cos(\omega t), \quad (19)$$

$$\text{si} = \sin(\alpha\varphi + \chi z) \sin(\omega t), \quad (20)$$

$$\text{coc} = \cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z) \sin(\omega t), \quad (21)$$

$$\text{sic} = \sin(\alpha\varphi + \chi z) \cos(\omega t), \quad (22)$$

By direct substitution, one can make sure that functions (10-18) transform the system of equations (1-9) with four arguments r, ϕ, z, t into

a system of equations with one argument and unknown functions $h(r), e(r), i(r)$. This system of equations is as follows:

$$\frac{e_r(r)}{r} + e'_r(r) - \frac{e_\phi(r)}{r} \alpha - \chi \cdot e_z(r) = 0, \quad (21)$$

$$-\frac{1}{r} \cdot e_z(r) \alpha + e_\phi(r) \chi - \frac{\mu\omega}{c} h_r = 0, \quad (22)$$

$$e_r(r) \chi - e'_z(r) + \frac{\mu\omega}{c} h_\phi = 0, \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{e_\phi(r)}{r} + e'_\phi(r) - \frac{e_r(r)}{r} \cdot \alpha + \frac{\mu\omega}{c} h_z = 0, \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{h_r(r)}{r} + h'_r(r) + \frac{h_\phi(r)}{r} \alpha + \chi \cdot h_z(r) = 0, \quad (25)$$

$$\frac{1}{r} h_z(r) \alpha - h_\phi(r) - i_r(r) = 0, \quad (26)$$

$$-h_r(r) \chi - \dot{h}_z(r) - i_\phi(r) = 0, \quad (27)$$

$$\frac{h_\phi(r)}{r} + \dot{h}_\phi(r) - \frac{h_r(r)}{r} \alpha - i_z(r) = 0. \quad (28)$$

$$\frac{i_r(r)}{r} + i'_r(r) + \frac{i_\phi(r)}{r} \alpha + \chi \cdot i_z(r) = 0. \quad (29)$$

Next, we introduce into consideration the coefficient k , which connects the functions h and e :

$$h_r = k e_r, \quad (30)$$

$$h_\phi = -k e_\phi. \quad (31)$$

$$h_z = -k e_z. \quad (32)$$

We perform the change of variables according to (30-32) in equations (21-29) and rewrite them

$$\frac{e_r}{r} + \dot{e}_r - \frac{e_\phi}{r} \alpha - \chi e_z = 0, \quad (33)$$

$$-\frac{e_z}{r} \alpha + e_\phi \chi - \frac{\mu\omega}{c} k e_r = 0, \quad (34)$$

$$-\dot{e}_z + e_r \chi - k \frac{\mu\omega}{c} e_\phi = 0, \quad (35)$$

$$\frac{e_\phi}{r} + \dot{e}_\phi - \frac{e_r}{r} \alpha + k \frac{\mu\omega}{c} e_z = 0, \quad (36)$$

$$k \frac{e_r}{r} + k \dot{e}_r - k \frac{e_\phi}{r} \alpha - k \chi e_z = 0, \quad (37)$$

$$-k \frac{e_z}{r} \alpha + k e_\phi \chi - i_r = 0, \quad (38)$$

$$k \dot{e}_z - k e_r \chi - i_\phi = 0, \quad (39)$$

$$-k \frac{e_\phi}{r} - k \dot{e}_\phi + k \frac{e_r}{r} \alpha - i_z = 0, \quad (40)$$

$$\frac{i_r}{r} + i'_r + \frac{i_\phi}{r} \alpha + \chi \cdot i_z = 0. \quad (41)$$

Note that equations (33) and (40) coincide for

$$i_z = -k \chi e_z \quad (42)$$

Note that equations (34) and (38) coincide for

$$i_r = \frac{\mu\omega}{c} k e_r. \quad (43)$$

Note that equations (35) and (39) coincide for

$$i_\varphi = k \frac{\mu\omega}{c} e_\varphi. \quad (44)$$

Note that equations (36) and (40) coincide for

$$i_z = -k \frac{\mu\omega}{c} e_z. \quad (45)$$

Из (42, 45) находим:

$$\chi = \frac{\mu\omega}{c} \quad (46)$$

Considering (33, 41, 44, 45), we note that equations (33, 41) coincide. Finally, equations (33) and (37) coincide.

Thus, equations (37-41) can be excluded from the system of equations and replaced by conditions (42-46). The remaining 4 equations (33-36) are a system of differential equations with three unknowns e_r, e_φ, e_z . Let's rewrite (33-36) taking into account (46) and get:

$$\frac{e_r}{r} + \dot{e}_r - \frac{e_\varphi}{r} \alpha - \chi e_z = 0, \quad (47)$$

$$-\frac{e_z}{r} \alpha + e_\varphi \chi - \chi k e_r = 0, \quad (48)$$

$$-\dot{e}_z + e_r \chi - k \chi e_\varphi = 0, \quad (49)$$

$$\frac{e_\varphi}{r} + \dot{e}_\varphi - \frac{e_r}{r} \alpha + k \chi e_z = 0. \quad (50)$$

Adding (48, 49), we get:

$$-\dot{e}_z - \frac{e_z}{r} \alpha + \chi(1-k)(e_\varphi + e_r) = 0, \quad (51)$$

or

$$(e_\varphi + e_r) = \frac{1}{\chi(1-k)} \left(\dot{e}_z + \frac{\alpha}{r} e_z \right), \quad (52)$$

Adding (47, 50), we get:

$$\frac{1}{r} (e_\varphi + e_r) + \frac{d}{dr} (e_\varphi + e_r) - \frac{\alpha}{r} (e_\varphi + e_r) - (1-k) \chi e_z = 0$$

or

$$\frac{d}{dr} (e_\varphi + e_r) + \frac{1-\alpha}{r} (e_\varphi + e_r) - (1-k) \chi e_z = 0 \quad (53)$$

Combining (52, 53), we get:

$$\frac{1}{\chi(1-k)} \frac{d}{dr} \left(\dot{e}_z + \frac{\alpha}{r} e_z \right) + \frac{1-\alpha}{r} \cdot \frac{1}{\chi(1-k)} \left(\dot{e}_z + \frac{\alpha}{r} e_z \right) - (1-k) \chi e_z = 0$$

or

$$\left(\ddot{e}_z + \frac{\alpha}{r} \dot{e}_z - \frac{\alpha}{r^2} e_z \right) + \frac{1-\alpha}{r} \left(\dot{e}_z + \frac{\alpha}{r} e_z \right) - (1-k)^2 \chi^2 e_z = 0$$

or

$$\ddot{e}_z + \left(\frac{\alpha}{r} + \frac{1-\alpha}{r} \right) \dot{e}_z + \left(-\frac{\alpha}{r^2} + \frac{1-\alpha}{r} \cdot \frac{\alpha}{r} - (1-k)^2 \chi^2 \right) e_z = 0 \quad (54)$$

We got the Bessel equation. According to (46), we can take

$$\chi \approx 0 \quad (55)$$

Then equation (54) takes the form:

$$\ddot{e}_z + \frac{1}{r} \dot{e}_z + \frac{\alpha^2}{r^2} e_z = 0 \quad (56)$$

The solution to this equation has the form

$$e_z = Ar^\alpha, \quad (57)$$

where A is some constant. Indeed, substituting (57) into (56), we obtain

$$(\alpha - 1)\alpha r^{\alpha-2} + \frac{\alpha}{r} r^{\alpha-1} - \frac{\alpha^2}{r^2} r^\alpha = 0$$

or

$$(\alpha - 1)\alpha + \alpha - \alpha^2 = 0,$$

which is an identity.

It is important to note that for $\alpha < 0$ it follows from (57) that the intensity increases with increasing radius, which can explain the skin effect without additional assumptions.

Now we find e_φ and e_r , assuming that

$$e_\varphi = AN r^{\alpha-1}, \quad (58)$$

$$e_r = AMr^{\alpha-1}, \quad (59)$$

where M and N are unknowns. Substituting (58, 59) in (48, 49), we find:

где M и N - неизвестные. Подставляя (58, 59, 57в) в (48, 49), находим:

$$-\frac{\alpha}{r} Ar^{2-\alpha} + \chi AN r^{\alpha-1} - \chi k AM r^{\alpha-1} = 0,$$

$$-\alpha Ar^{\alpha-1} + \chi AM r^{1-\alpha} - k \chi AN r^{\alpha-1} = 0$$

or

$$-\alpha + \chi N - \chi k M = 0, \quad (60)$$

$$-\alpha + \chi M - k \chi N = 0. \quad (61)$$

It is seen that $N = M$. Hence,

$$-\alpha + \chi(1 - k)N = 0,$$

or

$$N = M = \frac{\alpha}{\chi(1-k)}. \quad (62)$$

Thus,

$$e_r = e_\varphi = A \frac{\alpha}{\chi(1-k)} r^{1-\alpha}. \quad (64)$$

Obviously,

$$i = e/\rho, \quad (66)$$

where ρ is the resistivity. Moreover, from (42, 46) we find:

$$\rho = -\frac{1}{k\chi}. \quad (67)$$

Since the values of Q are known, we obtain:

$$k = -\frac{1}{\chi\rho}. \quad (68)$$

From (43-46, 68) we get:

$$i_z = e_z/\rho, \quad (69)$$

$$i_r = -e_z/\rho, \quad (70)$$

$$i_\varphi = -e_z/\rho. \quad (71)$$

So, the solution has the form of equations (10-22), where

- the functions $e(r)$ are defined by (64, 57),
- the functions $i(r)$ are defined by (69,70,71),
- the functions $h(r)$ are defined by (30, 31, 32, 68).

Let's find another voltage on a wire with a length L

$$U = \int_0^L E_z dz = e_z \int_0^L \text{co} \cdot dz. \quad (72)$$

3. Energy flows

The flux density of electromagnetic energy - the Poynting vector is determined by the formula

$$S = \eta E \times H, \quad (1)$$

where

$$\eta = c/4\pi. \quad (2)$$

In cylindrical coordinates r, ϕ, z , the electromagnetic energy flux density has three components S_r, S_ϕ, S_z directed along the radius, along the circumference, along the axis, respectively [1]. They are determined by the formula

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} S_r \\ S_\phi \\ S_z \end{bmatrix} = \eta(E \times H) = \eta \begin{bmatrix} E_\phi H_z - E_z H_\phi \\ E_z H_r - E_r H_z \\ E_r H_\phi - E_\phi H_r \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

or, taking into account the previous formulas,

$$S_r = \eta(e_\phi h_z - e_z h_\phi) \text{co} \cdot \text{si}, \quad (4)$$

$$S_\phi = \eta(e_z h_r \text{co}^2 - e_r h_z \text{si}^2), \quad (5)$$

$$S_z = \eta(e_r h_\phi \text{si}^2 - e_\phi h_r \text{co}^2). \quad (6)$$

Substituting here (2.33-2.35, 2.68-2.70), we get:

$$S_r = \eta(-ke_\phi e_z + ke_z e_\phi) \text{co} \cdot \text{si}, \quad (7)$$

$$S_\phi = \eta(ke_z e_r \text{co}^2 + ke_r e_z \text{si}^2) = \eta ke_r e_z, \quad (8)$$

$$S_z = \eta(-ke_r e_\phi \text{si}^2 - ke_\phi e_r \text{co}^2) = -\eta ke_r e_\phi. \quad (9)$$

Substituting (2.64, 2.65) here, we find that there are two energy fluxes in the wire with a density

$$S_{\varphi} = \eta k A^2 \frac{1}{2\chi} r^{2\alpha-1}, \quad (10)$$

$$S_z = -\eta k A^2 \frac{2\alpha-1}{4\chi^2} r^{2\alpha-2}. \quad (11)$$

Given these known densities, the unknowns A and α can be found from (10, 11).

References

1. S.I. Khmelnik. Inconsistency Solution of Maxwell's Equations. 16th edition, 2020, ISBN 978-1-365-23941-0. Printed in USA, Lulu Inc., ID 19043222, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3833821>